

From design constraints to control architecture: the EST first-light SCAO system

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ABSTRACT

The European Solar Telescope (EST) requires advanced adaptive optics (AO) to achieve high-resolution observations under challenging daytime conditions. The baseline system for first light is a Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) architecture, designed within the constraints of the telescope optical configuration, including the absence of an image de-rotator and the distribution of instruments across multiple focal stations.

We present the rationale for adopting a dual-arm AO concept combining the adaptive secondary mirror (ASM) with an additional deformable mirror in the visible arm. This approach improves performance at low elevation angles by mitigating chromatic effects. The control strategy is based on two independent loops associated with each spectral arm.

The distribution of wavefront sensing units across the Coudé rooms and the implications for system design are also discussed. The proposed architecture is fully compatible with a baseline evolution toward Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO), which has been considered from the outset of the EST design.

Keywords: SCAO, solar astronomy, European Solar Telescope, daytime seeing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive optics (AO) will play a central role in enabling the European Solar Telescope (EST) to reach its scientific objectives, which require high spatial, spectral, and temporal resolution under challenging daytime observing conditions. Unlike nighttime telescopes, daytime observations impose additional constraints related to high photon flux, strong atmospheric turbulence at low elevation angles, and the need for simultaneous multi-wavelength observations across different instruments.

Rather than being an independent subsystem, the AO architecture in EST is embedded in the overall optical concept of the telescope. Design choices such as the use of an adaptive secondary mirror (ASM), the absence of an image de-rotator, and the distribution of instruments across separate spectral arms directly affect how wavefront correction must be implemented and controlled, which introduces non-trivial constraints on wavefront sensing, control strategies, and correction distribution [1].

For first light, EST adopts a Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) approach that prioritizes robustness and operational simplicity, while preserving a clear upgrade path toward a Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) system.

This paper presents the reasoning that led to the adoption of a dual-arm AO concept for first light, combining correction at the ASM with an additional deformable mirror located in the visible arm. The implications of this approach are discussed in terms of performance, operational flexibility, and compatibility with future MCAO upgrades.

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2. TELESCOPE DESIGN CONSTRAINTS DRIVING THE AO ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Optical configuration

The design of the EST adaptive optics system is strongly driven by the telescope optical configuration and operational requirements. EST is based on an on-axis Gregorian design with a 4.2-meter monolithic primary mirror and an ASM used as the main wavefront corrector [2]. The full telescope layout is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall optical layout of the European Solar Telescope (EST). The location of the Gregorian focus is indicated by a red cross. The red inset highlights the pointing mirrors (M3–M6), which are optically conjugated to atmospheric layers and foreseen as MCAO deformable mirror locations. The blue inset shows a detailed view of the Pier Optical Path (POP) elements.

Light from the Gregorian focus is routed towards the Coudé instrument rooms through a sequence of four folding mirrors, which are arranged in crossed pairs to minimize polarimetric effects during telescope pointing, see Figure 1 red inset. These mirrors are optically conjugated to different atmospheric layers to be replaced progressively by deformable mirrors as part of the MCAO upgrade. Table 1 summarizes the conjugation altitude of each mirror projected at zenith, together with their effective diameter and the corresponding power density under expected maximum flux conditions, representing a worst-case scenario for thermal load.

Table 1 Conjugate altitudes of the EST folding mirrors (M3–M6), including corresponding clear aperture diameters and estimated incident power densities

Mirror	Conjugated altitude at zenith (km)	Diameter (mm)	Power density (kW/m ²)
M3	20	64.8	24.7
M4	12	76.5	17.1
M5	9	86.4	13.0
M6	5	119.3	6.7

2.2 Spectral separation, chromatic effects and dual-arm AO design

Due to space limitations, the scientific instruments are hosted in two Coudé rooms located below the telescope structure and are fed through the Pier Optical Path (POP), a thermally controlled refractive system designed to deliver a diffraction-limited focal plane to each room at a f-number of approximately F/50, while preserving well-defined pupil planes along the optical path.

Achieving the required chromatic performance over the full wavelength range (380–2200 nm) within a common refractive path was not feasible. Taking into account the dual Coudé room configuration, the optical design therefore adopts a spectral beam split within the POP, allowing the implementation of differential corrective elements in each arm and improving the overall optical performance. Thus, within the POP, a dichroic element separates the visible and red/infrared channels. The selection of the cut-off wavelength (680nm) is driven by the need to preserve the key spectral lines targeted by the EST science case, while ensuring a balanced distribution of instruments between both channels, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. EST science spectral lines over the solar spectrum. The cut-off wavelength of the POP dichroic (~680 nm) is indicated, illustrating the spectral separation between the visible and red/infrared channels while preserving key diagnostic lines.

Being the POP a refractive system, inherently introduces residual chromatic aberrations despite an optimized optical design. These instrumental chromatic effects must be accounted for in the AO system design. In addition to these internal contributions, the operational conditions of daytime observations further exacerbate undesirable chromatic effects. In solar observations, it is common to operate at large zenith angles where atmospheric dispersion introduces a strong wavelength-dependent effect. This contribution was explicitly assessed within the EST AO error budget, showing that operating the wavefront sensing at shorter wavelengths (e.g., around 500 nm) leads to a significant performance degradation at longer science wavelengths under these conditions [3].

These findings, together with the availability of two spectrally separated optical paths inherent to the POP design, motivated a reassessment of the initial AO concept for EST first light, which was originally based on a single correction loop operating at a reference wavelength of 500 nm and controlling the ASM. This baseline represents a standard and robust solution for solar telescopes, minimizing system complexity while providing global wavefront correction. However, the observed limitations of this configuration led to the exploration of an alternative architecture based on two independent sensing and correction branches, hereafter referred to as the dual-arm AO concept.

Different configurations were analyzed, varying sensing wavelengths and control distribution. The best performance was obtained with the primary correction loop shifted to operate at approximately 680 nm, associated with the red arm, while an additional high-order wavefront sensing channel is introduced at around 500 nm for the visible arm. The performance comparison between single-arm and dual-arm configurations is shown in Figure 3. It is important to highlight that this

effect is only observed at elevation angles below 30 degrees, while at higher elevations both configurations exhibit similar behaviour.

Figure 3. Performance comparison between single-arm and dual-arm AO control configurations under two representative seeing conditions. The selected dual-arm configuration shows improved performance, particularly at low elevation angles.

In addition, the dual-arm architecture may also offer advantages in terms of vibration mitigation, since the two instrument rooms are physically separated and independent sensing paths could improve the identification and compensation of differential disturbances. This aspect was further investigated through preliminary dynamic analyses of the telescope structure. These studies were driven by the stringent image stability requirement, specified to be below 4 mas RMS under closed-loop AO operation. As a result, a fast tip-tilt camera has been implemented in the red arm to correct residual image motion and ensure compliance with this requirement. In contrast, the same approach was not extended to the visible arm, where the limited photon flux and increased system complexity did not justify a ~10% of improvement in the performance gain under operational conditions.

As mentioned, the adoption of the dual-arm concept is further facilitated by the existing optical design. In particular, the visible arm includes an accessible pupil plane within the POP, allowing the integration of a second deformable mirror (M7-DM) without major modifications to the telescope layout. Based on these results, the dual-arm AO architecture is selected as the baseline for EST first light, providing improved performance under realistic observing conditions while maintaining compatibility with future MCAO upgrades.

Beyond chromatic effects, the multi-instrument and dual-arm nature of the telescope introduces additional system-level constraints. The simultaneous operation of multiple instruments prevents independent optimization of non-common path aberrations (NCPA) at telescope level, requiring final calibration and correction to be performed locally at instrument level through dedicated procedures and software compensation.

2.3 Distribution of wavefront sensing units in the Coudé rooms

Each wavefront sensing and control unit is integrated within the corresponding Coudé Sensing Assembly (CSA) of the red and visible arms. This partition reflects the dual-arm architecture of EST and ensures a clear physical and functional separation between wavefront sensing, telescope control, and science instrumentation.

The Red CSA hosts the high-order Red WFS together with the Fast Tip-Tilt (FTT) Camera. As will be detailed in the control architecture, the Red CSA provides the main input for the ASM control. Moreover, the FTT camera has two modes of operation to ensure robust image stabilization under varying seeing conditions: a high-precision mode for stable conditions and an extended field mode for degraded seeing.

In the visible CSA, the Vis WFS is dedicated to wavefront sensing and is designed to drive the M7 deformable mirror, enabling differential correction within the visible arm. The Full-field Imaging Camera is also allocated in this CSA. It provides a contextual view of the entire telescope field and operates in two modes: a full-field context mode for general monitoring and acquisition, and an AO verification mode with reduced field and higher spatial sampling to assess correction quality and system performance.

The Vis CSA also includes the Off-limb WFS intended for observations of solar prominences outside the solar disk. These structures emit strongly in H α (656 nm), which defines the operating wavelength for this mode [4]. Given the required narrow-band filtering, the available photon flux is significantly reduced, requiring a dedicated optical configuration of the Coudé Light Distribution system of the telescope. This subsystem is currently under requirements definition and is not part of the first-light baseline; at this stage, only a reserved physical location within the Vis CSA optical bench has been allocated.

A preliminary design of the main sensing and imaging units described above has been completed. Their key characteristics and functional roles are summarized in Figure 4, which highlights the current baseline configuration of each element within the overall AO architecture.

Figure 4. Functional diagram of the Red and Visible Coudé Sensing Assemblies (CSA), showing the main sensing and imaging elements and their roles within the EST AO architecture. The Vis WFS controls the ASM only when the red arm is not in operation. In this configuration, a Low-Pass Filter (LPF) is applied to offload the low-order modes onto the ASM, while the high-order (HO) correction is maintained by the M7-DM.

2.4 Pupil rotation

A distinctive feature of the EST optical design is the absence of an image de-rotator. As a consequence, both field and pupil rotation must be handled at the adaptive optics (AO) system level, with different implications for the visible and red arms, as schematic in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Illustration of components affected by pupil rotation.

In the visible arm, the pupil rotates at the same angular rate on both the DM-M7 and the Vis WFS. This co-rotation preserves the geometrical mapping between sub-apertures and actuators, and therefore no rotation of the interaction matrix (IM) is required. The main impact is limited to the rotation of partially obscured sub-apertures due to the telescope spider, which can be handled through masking strategies or real-time rejection of low-illumination signals.

In contrast, the red arm exhibits a relative rotation between the Red WFS and the ASM. This leads to a time-dependent misregistration between WFS sub-apertures and DM actuators, which must be compensated to maintain AO performance. The adopted strategy consists of updating (or equivalently rotating) the interaction matrix to account for the evolving mapping. Based on the expected pupil rotation rates, this update must be performed on timescales ranging from a few tens of seconds down to a few seconds under worst-case conditions, ensuring that the misregistration remains within acceptable limits.

Different approaches can be considered to address this effect, including optical derotation at the WFS level [5] or numerical compensation through control matrix updates [6]. In the current baseline design, a software-based solution is foreseen, avoiding additional opto-mechanical complexity while providing sufficient flexibility to accommodate the expected rotation rates.

3. CONTROL ARCHITECTURE AND DISTRIBUTION CORRECTION

The dual-arm AO concept requires a control strategy capable of efficiently distributing the wavefront correction between the ASM the deformable mirror located in the visible arm (M7-DM), while maintaining system stability and limiting

implementation complexity. In the adopted architecture, the ASM acts as the global corrector of the system. Being the aperture stop of the system and located upstream of the spectral split, it is seen by all instruments and is therefore responsible for compensating the dominant turbulence contributions across the full range of spatial frequencies in the red arm, including both low- and high-order aberrations. In the visible arm, the ASM provides a first-stage global correction, reducing the overall wavefront error prior to local refinement.

The DM-M7 operates exclusively within the visible arm and is dedicated to correcting residuals and non-common path aberrations specific to this channel. This distribution of correction has played a key role in relaxing the requirements of the ASM. By shifting part of the high-order correction in the visible range to M7-DM, the ASM can be optimized for longer wavelengths, reducing actuator density and overall system complexity while remaining within a technologically mature regime.

The control architecture follows a dual-loop approach. The Red WFS, together with FTT camera, which operate at 680nm, provide the main input to the ASM control loop, ensuring both global wavefront correction and image stabilisation. In parallel, the Vis WFS, which operates at 500nm, drives the M7-DM, enabling local refinement of the correction in the visible channel.

Both control loops operate simultaneously but remain largely independent. This approach provides a pragmatic solution for first-light operations, avoiding the complexity of a fully coupled multi-mirror control scheme while still enabling effective correction across both spectral channels. In the nominal dual-arm observing mode, the ASM reduces the overall wavefront error seen by both arms, while M7-DM compensates residual errors in the visible channel, maximizing performance at shorter wavelengths.

A dedicated operational mode is foreseen for off-limb observations. In this case, the off-limb WFS shares the same optical path as the on-disk visible WFS and is selected through an optical switching mechanism, ensuring mutually exclusive operation. Due to the different signal conditions and sensing requirements, this configuration represents the only case in which the visible WFS directly drives the ASM. This behavior is illustrated within the overall control scheme shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Control architecture diagram of the EST AO system, showing the main control loop (ASM), the secondary loop (M7-DM), and the dedicated off-limb operational mode (functional diagram, not a faithful representation of the optical train). The element labeled DC corresponds to the dichroic beamsplitter, which defines the spectral separation between the red and visible arms. The blocks C1, C2, and C3 represent independent control units associated with each loop.

4. UPGRADE PATH TOWARD MCAO

The AO architecture proposed for EST first light has been developed with a clear upgrade path toward a Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) system. This transition is essential to achieve uniform high-resolution correction over a wider field of view, addressing one of the key science requirements of the telescope.

The baseline MCAO concept builds upon the existing system by maintaining the ASM as the ground-layer (GL) corrector, while introducing additional deformable mirrors conjugated to higher atmospheric layers. These mirrors will replace the current pointing mirrors (M3-M6), which are already optically conjugated to specific altitudes, thereby minimizing the need for major modifications to the optical design.

Figure 7. Conceptual implementation of the MCAO architecture in EST, showing the ASM as ground-layer corrector and the additional altitude-conjugated deformable mirrors integrated into the optical path.

The selected conjugation heights span the lower and middle atmosphere, typically covering altitudes from approximately 5 km up to 20 km. This range provides sensitivity to the dominant turbulent layers relevant for high-resolution solar observations. A key driver for this design is the requirement to operate at low elevation angles (down to $\sim 15^\circ$), where the increased atmospheric path enhances the contribution of high-altitude turbulence. Under these conditions, the inclusion of multiple altitude-conjugated deformable mirrors becomes essential. The MCAO system is therefore foreseen to operate with the ASM combined with up to two additional DMs, depending on observing conditions and elevation.

Wavefront sensing in the MCAO configuration will be based on a multi-directional approach implemented in the red arm (Main loop), enabling the reconstruction of the three-dimensional turbulence profile. This approach is currently under laboratory validation. In case the performance is not satisfactory, alternative strategies, such as a field-splitting scheme, will be considered. The visible arm (Secondary loop) is expected to retain its current role, controlling the M7-DM and providing high-resolution correction for its dedicated channel. A simplified overview of the MCAO architecture is shown in Figure 7.

While this upgrade path is conceptually straightforward, several challenges must be addressed:

- All deformable mirrors are required to share consistent optical coatings in order to preserve the polarimetric performance of the telescope, imposing strong constraints on technology selection and system integration.
- The mirrors are located at positions where the solar irradiance remains significant, leading to high thermal loads that must be carefully managed.

- The different mirrors experience distinct rotation dynamics due to their positions along the optical path, increasing the complexity of calibration and real-time control.

To address these challenges, dedicated simulation and experimental efforts are underway. A new simulation framework, SAOS, is being developed to capture the specific characteristics of the EST MCAO system, including rotation effects and multi-layer turbulence reconstruction [7]. In parallel, a laboratory demonstrator has been established to validate key aspects of the design and to explore mitigation strategies. This combined approach enables a progressive and controlled transition from the first-light SCAO system to a full MCAO implementation [8].

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have presented the design rationale, control philosophy, and implementation choices of the adaptive optics system for the first light of the European Solar Telescope.

Starting from the constraints imposed by the telescope optical design and scientific requirements, we have shown how these factors naturally lead to a dual-arm AO architecture. This approach addresses key limitations of a single-loop system, particularly in terms of chromatic effects when pointing at low elevation angles.

The proposed control strategy relies on a hierarchical distribution of correction between the adaptive secondary mirror and a deformable mirror located in the visible arm. This configuration enables efficient operation while maintaining a manageable level of complexity at first light.

Different operational modes have been defined to support a wide range of observing scenarios, including simultaneous multi-instrument observations and specialized off-limb measurements.

Finally, the system has been designed with a clear upgrade path toward MCAO, leveraging existing optical elements and incorporating both simulation and experimental validation efforts to address the associated challenges.

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